

FOUNDATIONS FOR QUALIFYING VOLUNTARY DONATION FROM COMMITTING A CRIME IN CRIMINAL LAW

Gapparova Sevara Khikmatulla kizi

Student of Karakalpak State University named after Berdaq
sevagapporova@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7980673>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 23-May 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 26-May 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 29-May 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

*voluntary return from
committing a crime,
preparation for a crime,
attempt to commit, the
completed assassination*

ABSTRACT

this article explains the concept of voluntary return from the commission of a crime, its peculiarities, similar and different aspects of it from the completed crime and the assassination of a crime. The importance of criminal justice qualification to correctly determine the voluntary return from committing a crime has also been covered in detail by the qaday resolution of the voluntary return issue if the crime was committed in participation.

Criminal legal activity, as indicated above, goes through several stages. Stages are in some cases separated from each other by a time interval. Sometimes, however, the specific stage itself may cease to continue the criminal activity that the individual initiated during the passage of time intervals. Voluntary return from committing a crime is important in criminal law because it excludes liability. That is why it is of great importance in the implementation of the tasks of crime prevention and Prevention.

In criminal law, a voluntary return from committing a crime is understood to mean that a person ceases the criminal activity that he has begun, realizing that there is an opportunity to bring it to an end, or prevents the emergence of a criminal consequence. It provides for the refusal of an individual to carry out his criminal activities, voluntary and complete return.

A voluntary return from committing a crime does not include a refusal to return actions that did not lead to the intended criminal consequence. It is necessary to be able to distinguish a voluntary return from the commission of a crime from a refusal to return actions that did not lead to the criminal consequence that the person intended. For example, Zhurayev watches over Gofurov in his wake in an attempt to kill him, and shoots a pistol at him from a deserted place, where there are few people, but the bullet does not touch the victim. Zhurayev shoots at Gofurov for the second time, which also does not hit the target. The culprit then escapes from the scene. Even if zhurayev's actions are aimed at deliberate murder, he willingly returns from continuing his criminal activities, since he can conclude that there was every opportunity to fulfill the goal. Such an opinion is a mistake, because, Zhurayev twice shoots at the victim, in both of which the bullet does not touch the victim, regardless of his will. Then he will not continue his efforts. There is a complete composition of the first two actions of the culprit - the assassination attempt on the Dayo. Based on these

signs, the act is qualified by Article 25 of the JC, Part 2 and the corresponding part of Article 97, paragraph 2.

If the victim is not hit by the first shot, when the second shot hits the target, and the person who shoots for various reasons, even if the victim is provided with first aid, the qualification issue will be resolved as in the case above. The fact that the culprit provided the victim with first aid does not affect qualification, but can be taken into account when prescribing a penalty.

Voluntary return from committing a crime can occur at both stages of non-stop criminal activity. It should take into account the nature of incomplete criminal activity, at what stage the person voluntarily returned from committing a crime, the role of the individual in committing a crime. In all cases where the voluntary return of a person from bringing the crime to an end is established under the criminal law of the Republic, it is necessary to take into account the issue of decriminalization according to his voluntary return.

Voluntary return from committing a crime can also occur in the stages of preparing for a crime and an attempt to commit it. Some scholars have expressed the view that voluntary return from committing a crime is possible only in the incomplete type of assassination attempt, and voluntary return from committing an assassination attempt is impossible. The opinion of such authors cannot be agreed. Voluntary return from committing a crime also occurs in an assassination attempt. True, in one-minute crimes there will be no voluntary return, and this is a case to be taken into account in qualifying. For example, it is impossible to voluntarily return from a crime after the full implementation of actions aimed at the implementation of the goal in crimes such as manslaughter, injury to the body, etc., since the culprit performs all the actions that he considers necessary to fulfill his goal, but the criminal outcome does not occur in cases unrelated to him. In such crimes, a criminal consequence occurs immediately after the execution of an action (inaction) that constitutes the objective side of the content. A sluggish (passive) type of voluntary return from committing a crime can occur in the preparatory and assassination stages of criminal activity. The active (active) type, on the other hand, sets in existence only in an assassination attempt.

When there is a certain time interval between an action and a planned criminal outcome in a completed assassination attempt, the person may voluntarily return from fulfilling their criminal purpose. In this time frame, there will be an opportunity to prevent a criminal consequence in a person. In such cases, there is a complete basis for stimulating the actions of the individual, since the individual can prevent the occurrence of a criminal consequence with his active actions. In an assassination attempt, there will be only an active type of voluntary return from committing a crime. The person only actively acts to prevent a criminal consequence after the full execution of actions. In an attempt that is complete with inaction, it is impossible to voluntarily return from committing a crime.

In a complete assassination attempt, the person must be taken in a voluntary return from committing a crime, having received the expected harmful consequence to qualify the act. If, despite the actions carried out, a criminal consequence occurs, the crime committed is qualified on a general basis. The actions of the culprit aimed at preventing a criminal consequence cannot serve as a basis for decriminalization. They can only be taken into account when imposing a sentence by the court. If, as a result of such actions, the person partially prevents the expected criminal consequence and a milder consequence arises than

the expected consequence, the question of qualification is solved differently. For example, Pirmatov, trying to shoot his wife behind jealousy, gives her poison, after a while his wife's rake comes, and gives her another drug, which loses the strength of the poison. As a result, the victim's life is saved, but he is severely injured. In this case, criminal liability may be excluded under Article 26 of the JC for attempted murder of the culprit using the rules of voluntary return from committing a crime. A person is held liable only for the harmful consequences that he actually caused, and the act is qualified by Article 104 of the JC. According to the criminal law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, responsibility for the voluntary return of a person from committing a crime is excluded only if there is no other criminal composition in his actions, which he actually carried out.

In order to correctly determine the voluntary return from committing a crime, criminal legal qualification must be carried out clearly and clearly. With it, it is determined which crime this or that person voluntarily returned from committing and which crime he should be held responsible for. It is important to correctly determine the composition of the crime when it is determined which crime the person should be held responsible for. The act of a person who voluntarily returns from committing a crime excludes liability, and if there is a different composition of the crime in his actions, he is liable not for criminal activity that does not end in liability, but for a completed crime.

If the crime is committed in participation, the issue of voluntary return is solved differently. The actions of the participants are closely related to each other. Therefore, according to the role of participants in committing a crime, the features of their voluntary return from committing a crime are determined. In order for the organizer, signatory or assistant to be exempted from liability for participation under Part 5 of Article 30 of the JC, as a voluntary return from committing a crime, they must have taken all measures related to themselves in order to prevent a crime in time.

The organizer must have actively tried to prevent the crime committed by the executor in order to make a voluntary return from committing the crime. Despite all the active actions of the organizer, if the crime is not taken, the actions performed by him will not affect the qualification. They can only be taken into account when imposing punishment by the court. In order for the responsibility of the organizer to be excluded, he must have prevented the crime by his active actions.

The question of the criminal liability of the Testor for voluntary return from committing a crime is also solved as above. Voluntary return from committing a crime by an assistant can also be expressed in active and sluggish acts.

The voluntary return from committing a crime by the acting person is manifested in the form of sluggish behavior. In this, he refuses to continue the actions that cause a criminal consequence. This circumstance indicates that he voluntarily returned from committing a crime. If the executor performs all the actions that he finds necessary to achieve a criminal goal, and carries out certain actions on the Prevention of a criminal consequence, he will have actively acted.

Conclusion

Thus, in order to qualify a person as a voluntary return from committing a socially dangerous act, ujinoi must prevent a criminal consequence by performing all actions that are blind to stopping his actions or causing a criminal consequence, realizing the possibility of bringing

the activity to an end. A person must voluntarily and completely return from committing a crime at his own will, at his discretion, that is, criminal activity should not be suspended under external influences. In the implementation of the criminal justice qualification, it is necessary to determine a voluntary return from committing crimes, since they exclude liability, if there is no other independent criminal content in their actions. Voluntary return from committing a crime is of great importance in the Prevention of crimes and their prevention. The Institute of voluntary return from committing a crime provides for persons who have started criminal activities, the opportunity to return to normal life, and such acts should be encouraged.

References:

1. Criminal-executive code: T.: Justice " 2022
2. Order of the Minister of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 2012 No. 174 "on approval of the rules of internal order of penal institutions of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the type of imprisonment
3. Rustamboev M.H., Akhrorov B.J. etc. Criminal law. Textbook. - T.: Teacher, 2002. -208 b.
4. Kadirov R. Sovershenstvovanie pravovogo regulirovaniya I primeniya distsiplinarnix mer K osujdnim. - T.: Shark, 2002. - 187 P.
5. Abdukhalikov M.A., Payzullaev G., Abdukodirov Sh.Yo. Criminal-Executive law (Al'bom schemes). - T.TDYuI, 2005. -142 b.
6. Reviews of the criminal executive code. Editor in charge: yu.f.d., prof. M.H.Rustambaev. - T.: TDYuI, 2007. -574 PP

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY